

ISSUES OF DEVELOPING INVESTMENT ATTRACTION IN MODERN CONDITIONS

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Abstract: This article provides an analysis of what infrastructure needs to be formed in the process of attracting investment today, Uzbekistan's opportunities and ways in this direction. In addition, the results, status and financial turnover of investments in previous years are also given. In recent years, the ongoing socio-economic reforms in the country are also taking comprehensive measures to increase the volume of foreign investment in the country's economy.

In today's modern conditions, it is becoming increasingly important to provide production in the world economy with new equipment and technologies, to gain a place and position in the international market, to attract investment in the national economy to produce competitive and quality products.

Increasing investment in the national economy is also one of the key tasks in reducing the impact of the global crisis on the world community as a result of the spread of the COVID-19 pandemic, which is now a global phenomenon.

According to the scientific literature in the field, the methods of assessing the effectiveness of investments in the context of volatility and uncertainty of international markets require consideration of risk factors, regulation of investment and proper distribution between regions and economic sectors.

In recent years, the ongoing socio-economic reforms in the country are also taking comprehensive measures to increase the volume of foreign investment in the country's economy. In particular, the Action Strategy for the five priority areas of development of the Republic of Uzbekistan for 2017-2021 identifies priorities such as active attraction of foreign investment in the sectors and regions of the economy by improving the investment climate, effective use of foreign investments and loans. These tasks play an important role in pursuing an active investment policy aimed at modernization of production, technical and technological renewal, implementation of investment projects for the development of production and social infrastructure, as well as the creation of a favorable investment climate.

In a video conference on December 26, 2020 on "Preliminary results of 2020 and tasks for 2021 in the field of investment and foreign trade" against the background of a 40% decline in foreign direct investment worldwide and a 25% reduction in world trade in 2020, At the end of the year, the volume of foreign direct investment increased compared to the previous year and amounted to 6.6 billion soums. USD and the export index - 15.1 bln. dollars. It was noted that these indicators were achieved through the implementation of major investment projects in the production of construction materials, information and communication, electricity, chemical and light industries, as well as a significant increase in exports of goods and services in textiles, agriculture, mining and transport. According to the forecast, in 2021 the volume of foreign direct investment will reach 7.5 billion. USD, and the volume of exports amounted to 17 bln. dollars. The need for more effective organization of work to attract investors and increase export potential was emphasized.

It was noted that one of the most promising ways to achieve these goals is an objective analysis of the opportunities for entrepreneurs to expand existing production capacity and create new ones by attracting capital investment and modern technologies to the most efficient industries - "growth points".

Whatever the form of investment in the national economy, it will develop a competitive environment, accelerate the production of competitive products, as well as bring modern innovative, advanced equipment and technologies and diversify the economy. It should be noted that attracting investment will accelerate the production of high quality products or help to produce products that will replace existing products.

Foreign direct investment in the structure of foreign investment is important for the sustainable development of sectors of the economy, which can have a positive impact on economic development by accumulating more capital than the level of domestic savings, supporting the balance of payments and expanding import opportunities. Foreign direct investment plays an important role in improving the operation, production and capital efficiency of individual enterprises, the introduction of new technologies and the improvement of the management system. These processes help to develop the domestic market, increase the skills and practical experience of workers by indirectly influencing suppliers of goods and services, customers, competitors.

The active investment policy pursued by the state plays a special role in increasing the volume of investment in the country's economy. Investment policy is a function of the state to mobilize investment funds to organize the reproduction of material goods in society.

For the effective implementation of investment policy, it is expedient to establish a number of institutions that will serve to create a favourable investment climate. An effective model in the world economy relies on a market system and takes full advantage of the national economy. There is every reason to say that Uzbekistan has created a unique, favourable investment climate, a system of privileges and preferences for foreign investors. This is evidenced by the fact that the volume of foreign investment in the economy of our country is growing from year to year. In the implementation of the program of further deepening structural changes in the economy, accelerating the investment activities of enterprises, modernization of production, technical and technological re-equipment, it is necessary to attract foreign investment, primarily direct investment. This will allow for the widespread introduction of new technologies in the production process, the creation of new jobs and, on this basis, to ensure the sustainable development of the country's economy.

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